

Development Plan

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Executive Summary

This document aims to define a Development plan for Equal-Life’s toolbox considering the complexity and uniqueness of the future implementation scenarios. These scenarios involve different actors and roles within the stakeholders and the internal partners of the Equal-Life consortium ranging from the municipality level to associations, local bodies, and networks, down to individual users.

The initial design of the Equal-Life toolbox, born from the internal project discussion, will be continuously improved by external feedback during the co-design phase with the stakeholders, as illustrated in D8.3 (van den Hazel et al. 2022). Cooperation with stakeholders from different countries and organizations represents a key point in the toolbox development plan and allows the development team to widen the range of the targeted users.

This document reports the toolbox implementation strategy plan (Development plan). This approach heavily relies on three major methodology streams:

- **Explorative methodology:** involving technicians, experts, and potential stakeholders in the activity of designing multiple prototypes of the tools that will compose the toolbox;
- **Implementation methodology:** organizing and envisioning a development long term strategy
- **Governance methodology:** apply the strategies necessary for the dissemination and teaching of the toolbox to the different categories of target users

The present document is structured as follows:

1. A short introduction describing the primary purposes of the toolbox, the general idea behind its development, and its context within the Equal-Life project
2. A schematic representation of the development process.

The research team developing the toolbox will try to remain faithful to the strategies described in this document. However, exploiting a co-design process for creating a practical toolbox could produce unpredictable outputs that will affect future implementation strategies.

1. Introduction

In a complex scenario, such as studying factors that can influence human life, the Equal-Life project aims to study the effect of these physical and social factors on children's mental health and cognitive development. This will be achieved by analysing massive amounts of data and developing new data mining strategies to find statistical associations between exposures, the effect of exposures, and other potential mediators like stress/restoration, self-regulation/coping, and sleep with children's mental health. The results, ranging from analysis strategies to guidelines emerging from this complex research process, will be transferred to stakeholders like educational institutes, mental health institutes, and urban planners who deal with rising awareness and policy-making at the national and local levels. Furthermore, having guided access to information (i.e., the results of studies conducted in Equal-life, aggregated statistics of the data collected in the cohorts, enriched information, up-to-date documentation on the definitions of the concepts, and the interpretation of the published evidence) would facilitate the development of good governance practices. A toolbox at the end of the chain eases the access and dissemination of the results. No pre-built tools, such as the Equal-Life expected output, are available for managing a complex data ecosystem. Most of the available digital resources focus on supporting the end-user on the clinical and diagnostic aspects and not on the interaction with the infrastructure responsible for organizing, administering, and applying the resources debuted to managing mental health issues. In this document, the word "toolbox" refers to the set of tools that will be developed within the Equal-Life project and is used as synonymous with "toolkit". For this reason, the term "toolbox" refers to the object that includes all the tools.

1.1 Toolbox development context

The WP9, focused on developing the toolbox for semantic exploration and knowledge management, started in 2021 and will last until 2024 (See Gantt in Appendix). Several tasks take part in the toolbox development and implementation. Task 9.1 is already completed, Task 9.2 is still in progress, Task 9.3 and Task 9.4 are just started, and Task 9.5 is not yet in place. Figure 1 provides an overview of the interactions between the various tasks.

1.1.1 Collaborative Task Management: Facilitating Effective Work and Interaction

The team started (Regional Tools Integration - task 9.1) by searching for already existing tools related to the children's mental health and cognitive development that can inspire the development of the Equal-Life toolbox. The task's main aim is to review existing literature and tools to identify gaps and challenges the toolbox should address. All the resources (e.g., links to tools, documentation, events, etc.) are collected in a shared document, ordered, and commented. The document is still active and usable by all the project users and partners (<https://equal-life.healthandsafety.nl/do/document?id=39300-646f63756d656e74>). The ideas collected are used as a source of discussion for designing new modules and functionalities.

Task 9.2 aims to develop the core infrastructure of the data and knowledge exploration tool and the different tools designed during the project. An important step is to mediate between the needs of the users and stakeholders and the project's goals. The requirements gathering requires conducting user interviews, surveys, and focus groups and reviewing existing documentation and research (See section 2.1 - Exploration and Co-Design). To achieve this goal, the team plans to create a prototype of the tool, define the user interface, and select the appropriate technology to implement the tool (See section 2 -

Development strategy). With the design in place, the next step is to develop the data and knowledge exploration tool and test it to ensure it meets the requirements. The testing phase may involve user acceptance testing to ensure that the tool meets the needs of the different user categories and that stakeholders use it effectively (Development and deployment of regional interventions – task 9.4). The training, the live support, the maintenance, and the tool’s monitoring represent crucial tasks to guarantee quality and ease the toolbox’s adoption (Training- task 9.5). Throughout the development process, great importance will be placed on the fact that the tools are designed with user needs in mind, is easy to use, and is flexible enough to accommodate changing requirements and needs. The development of the Equal-Life handbook, in parallel with the toolbox’s development, will improve the user experience and ease access to the contents of the various toolbox modules (Handbook – task 9.3).

The handbook represents a comprehensive guide designed to help users navigate and exploit the features of the tools. It also helps to ensure consistency and standardization in using the toolbox across the project and facilitates knowledge sharing and collaboration among users.

In the project's final year, the team will focus on disseminating their work and outreach efforts to ensure that the toolbox will be widely adopted and integrated into existing workflows in administration and academia. In addition, the work will be presented at conferences, published research papers in academic journals, and engaged with potential users to gather feedback and improve the toolbox's usability (see section 2.3- Case studies).

Figure 1. A revised schema of project action integrations presented in D9.1. More details in the main text.

1.2 Vision of the toolbox structure

Due to the complex nature of concepts, definitions, and models produced from different work packages (Specifically: WP2, WP3, and WP4) the design strategy envisages the development of a modular software structure. Modular design allows us to decompose large, seemingly complex systems into small, manageable parts. The main idea is to separate the functionality of a program into independent, interchangeable modules, such that each contains everything necessary to execute only one aspect of the desired functionality. The strength of a project's modular design will ultimately determine how large it can scale. Without modular design, it would be impossible to manage the complexity of all but the smallest, most incremental projects.

Various actions have been hypothesized to be translated into many interactive modules. Figure 2 presents, in the form of actions, the results of the co-design process that started in Ljubljana during the

first Stakeholder Forum in March 2022 and was previously supported by surveys and interviews. The protocols and actions underlying this analysis process (two rounds of the Delphi survey and the first round of interviews with targeted questions) are described in detail in internal deliverables and will be the subject of scientific publications by the research team involved.

Figure 2 The Figure shows the *actions identified by the co-design process linked with the corresponding module*. Both objects (actions and modules) converge to the toolbox's main structure represented by the main page of the web application prototype. The training action uses the results and functions of the developed modules as a basis. *The icons on the right side represent the types of users identified as target audience.*

1.3 Actions and Toolbox Modules

Six main actions (report, visualise, explore, connect, share and train(ing)), have been identified that will be translated into four modules, as described in Figure 2.

Report: The constant transfer of up-to-date project results is a crucial aspect of the Equal-Life toolbox. The partners involved in the project are called to a summarisation action of the different results to enable the knowledge transfer to external partners. In particular, the main results to be transferred refer to the investigation of the research questions described in D1.2 (Selander et al., 2021).

The primary goal of the Stakeholders' module is to guide users in exploring the project's key concepts and actively involve stakeholders in project activities, such as designing new toolbox modules. The module is designed as an interactive web page that collects information from stakeholders while guiding them on a cognitive path. The collected data enables the system to evolve and automatically learn what

type of content should be presented to the different categories of users. A prototype of the tool is already available (see section 2 on development strategies for more details) and will be used as a tool during the meetings with stakeholders.

The Stakeholder's module represents the "open door" to the other modules to guide the stakeholders through the available resources.

The project's proposal and initial documentation refer to The Stakeholders' Module as "Demonstrator".

Visualization and Exploration:

Given the volume and the heterogeneity of the available and expected results of Equal-Life, a visualization tool is required to ease the user's exploration task.

Equal-Life primarily uses data from nine cohorts and three longitudinal and cross-sectional studies in school-aged children (N= > 250,000) from nine EU member states. The data include information about children (prenatal up to age 21) and their parents. The data will be enriched with intermediate effect biomarkers and external (physical and social) information. In addition, the project will collect data on school children (in Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands) to study the distinct mechanisms underlying the association of environmental exposures and mental health indicators, including physical and social aspects (stress/restoration, sleep, supportive environments for children self-regulation).

The project will access information about children's and adolescents' sleep patterns and sleep quality (Sweden; Austria) connected to environmental exposures and their effect on mental health. In addition, in a sample of schools, children's activity patterns in their age-relevant settings will be studied. Also, the time-activity patterns will be part of data collection in children and adolescents (in NL) and during experiments on children's auditory cognition (in Aachen, Germany).

Moreover, internal discussions extended on some occasions to stakeholders highlight the need to enable interactions with internal and external data sources at different levels of accessibility. The accessibility aspect is particularly relevant because of the different kinds of Toolbox end-users defined in the next section.

From these **two actions**, derive two toolbox modules the visualization module and the Semantic knowledge exploration module (see section 2.4 and 2.5).

Connection and Sharing: The panorama of realities dealing with children's mental health in the European area is extremely varied and rugged. The need to have a clear overview of each country's resources related to mental health emerged during the stakeholders' meeting. Furthermore, the rising interest in Equal-Life project highlighted a strong need for an exchange platform for publishing announcements and sharing information and opinion related to the project's theme.

The Connection and Sharing module is a response to these requests. It can ease the exchange of information between the parties. The application, similar to a blog, will have to allow the insertion of content and a feedback system.

Training: The dissemination and training represent the project's final phases (from 2024). The training actions will take place differently for the different modules and types of users (see the section below "audience toolbox"). The training activities exploit teaching tools, such as a go-to interaction app for hybrid meetings, online drawing, a whiteboard app, and notebooks. The Training action does not have a corresponding specific module. Instead, this action provides support in using and understanding the different modules of the toolbox.

1.2 The toolbox's audience. Definition of user types

In the prototyping phases, we hypothesized the toolbox's target user type. This paragraph briefly describes the various types of users to give the reader a complete overview of the context. [More details on users description are present in D9.1.](#)

Generally, the stakeholders involved in the Equal-Life project, who are users in the toolbox, are researchers, policymakers working at different levels of public administration, and professionals such as psychologists, sociologists, doctors, or teachers.

More specifically, we identify three types of users with different needs:

The Researcher: a user with a high level of knowledge in the technical domain (statisticians, technicians, researchers). In particular, they can analyze and interpret data. Their primary aims are to create new domain knowledge by conceptualizing the results at the local level. In the toolbox's current idea, these users will access the toolbox for information such as (aggregated) data, libraries, pipelines, and other tools for data analysis, evaluate their implementation, and propose improvements by using them in a research context. Moreover, they can collect their data and use the internal resources available from the toolbox to generate aggregated statistics (like libraries or pipelines, as previously described).

The Domain Expert: user who works in contact with the target (children 0-21 years old) that readily engages with technical material such as scientific publications, documentation, and aggregate data reports (e.g., psychologists, social workers, urban planners, paediatricians, administrative technicians, teachers). A Domain expert is responsible for transferring domain knowledge to policymakers by contextualizing it locally. In the current toolbox's formalization, these users need aggregated data exploration and would benefit from basic descriptive statistics and visualization tools. In addition, it would be responsible for collecting data at a local level and exploiting specific data ingestion tools. Therefore, target training for this user will focus on data exploration and visualization toolbox modules.

The Policymaker: high-level user who can influence the management policies of addressed issues (e.g., Planners, Administrators, politicians). It is the target of the project's documentation mainly focused on practical intervention (i.e., case studies or the logic model for equity impact assessment of interventions). Therefore, it should be able to use and exploit such documents, including advanced search and key concepts' visualisations.

2. Development strategy

2.1 Research methodology

This document reports the development approach of toolbox development followed for the entire duration of the Equal-Life project. Where possible, we describe in detail the implementation strategies of each module and provide the chosen methodology. The toolbox development stages described in this section are also represented in a Gantt chart in Annex 1 at the end of this document.

The methodology employed in the design/implementation task has explorative and creative components, consisting mainly of successive steps of divergent and convergent reasoning. The innovation approaches heavily rely on four main phases of research methodology, as shown in Figure 2:

- Explorative methodology: involving technical, experts, and potential stakeholders in the activity of multiple prototype designs of the tools that will compose the toolbox;
- Implementation methodology: organizing and envisioning a development long term strategy
- Governance methodology: coordinate toolbox implementation with long-term strategies with feedback and content derived from beta versions in use as a test
- Dissemination methodology: apply the needed strategies for disseminating and organizing training tailored for the different categories of target users.

Figure 3: Main scheme of the methodology followed in the design of the development plan.

The first two phases are cyclically applied over time until the complete definition of the toolbox prototype. The dissemination phase follows the implementation of each module and an internal review of the contents to be publicly shared (see Gantt graph in Annex 1)

2.1.1 Exploration and Co-Design

To address the first of the four reported goals, we adopted the following approach:

- Build robust knowledge of the data ecosystem and reframe the given boundaries (Sensing);
- Identify the future scenarios of the application and, for each scenario, provide stakeholders' profiles (Envisioning);
- Select the valuable scenarios and explore them with use cases (Selecting and Interpreting);

For instance, from the first stage of Sensing, the team was able to widen the scope of the Equal-Life challenges and ecosystem thanks to insights from different actors extracted from a set of interviews and target meetings.

The objective of the Sensing step is to apply a critical attitude to reframe the boundaries of the given directions for Equal-Life's toolbox deployment (as given during the kick-off meeting) and to identify scenarios for application and significant management implications. The sensing step allowed the researchers to validate and enrich the input from the project specification and the suggestions from the

active group of experts. By participating in actions put in place by WP8 as part of stakeholder engagement activities, the development team participated in interviews and customer journeys, representing the primary approach for the Sensing step. Still, the Stakeholder module (described in the next paragraph) plays a crucial role in this phase. In addition, the research team submitted surveys to potential stakeholders together with performed analysis.

2.1.1.1 Co-Design meetings

In accordance and co-participation with WP8 a formal co-design workshop and two stakeholder forum were set up to facilitate the process of information exchange between scientists and stakeholders (policymakers, regulators and research networks).

These three face-to-face meeting plays a crucial role in the prototype phase and represents the source of most of the considerations and actions described in this document.

- Stakeholder forum in Ljubljana, March 7 - 8, 2022
- Co-design workshop in Skopje, September 14 -15, 2022
- Stakeholder forum in Milan, Italy, November 16-17, 2022

The co-design process creates interaction with stakeholders within a design development process to ensure that the results meet their needs and are usable. Co-design is a transdisciplinary process; the result can be a report or product, such as a handbook or guideline. For example, in Equal-Life, co-design represents an engagement process that enables stakeholders to use project results for policy-making or draft interventions.

A Stakeholder Forum is an event, open to representatives of institutions, national, regional, and local authorities, and individual entities from different domains (e.g., higher education, research, associations, and civil society).

For a detailed description of the outputs of the event, see Deliverable 8.4 (Van Den Hazel 2023).

To provide an overview of the process that led to the current development plan, in the next sections we report the feedback related to the toolbox development.

Ljubljana

Around 25 people attended the live sessions, and an additional 20 joined online. The live attendees came from countries such as Slovenia, Croatia, Finland, Italy, and the Netherlands. Meanwhile, those who joined online came from Greece, Sweden, Slovakia, North Macedonia, and Germany. The group was split, with half of the attendees focusing on public (mental) health and the other half on the physical environment. In addition, several researchers from different countries and institutes involved in the Equal-Life project also participated in the sessions.

Feedback: During the event, the dev team presented the first toolbox mockup to stakeholders and got initial feedback on the toolbox definition for a project like Equal-Life. Feedback was mainly related to the needs of the stakeholders. It can be summarized as the need to establish an information network

and have easy access to explorable interpreted material (some of which has already been commented on by experts in the field).

Skopje

On September 14th and 15th, 2022, a co-design workshop was conducted in Skopje, North Macedonia, to discuss the progress and the interaction with stakeholders in the Equal-Life project. The main aim was to determine the best ways of using the expected project results for implementing policies or interventions and to identify the available tools and design policies that meet the needs of stakeholders working in the domain of children's mental health, cognitive development, or protecting the social or physical environment. The workshop also explored how science and civil society organizations can best cooperate. The workshop was conducted live, with 19 participants in attendance.

Feedback: to develop effective tools, it is crucial to understand the target group and create tailor-made products. Best practices should also be considered, but issues such as funding and staffing must be considered. Successful tools include Lifelines, which focuses on data collection and uses visual and interactive communication methods. It is essential to specify the (governmental) level being addressed and to use communication techniques like videos and storytelling to present data. In developing tools, it is necessary to avoid reinventing the wheel and to explore existing resources that can be used.

Milan

The purpose of the stakeholder forum in Milan was to facilitate a discussion among mental and environmental health professionals regarding three key topics: 1) the impact of children's physical and social environment on their development; 2) the use of tools to connect the scientific and policy domains; and 3) the usages of future Equal-Life project results for developing policies and interventions to enhance children's environments and mental health. In attendance were 17 stakeholders (part-time) and 23 researchers (5 of whom participated online) from the Equal-Life project.

Feedback: The activity was introduced with a brief presentation explaining the current definitions and purpose of the toolbox and handbook. These definitions were continuously discussed through feedback from both internal (Equal-Life) and external (stakeholder) partners. The current understanding is that the toolbox should provide tools to help those interested in the mental health and cognitive development of children and adolescents at different levels to explore and understand the results of the Equal-Life project. In addition, the handbook should accompany the toolbox as a guide to practical use and help the user understand the connections between the different results. Throughout the forum, participants were encouraged to share their impressions and ideas about the toolbox on sticky notes, which could be related or unrelated to the presented contents. The aim was to collect the participants' opinions on the topics covered and gather ideas for future toolbox and handbook content. The feedback focused on developing tools that could facilitate access to project deliverables, research questions, and analysis features. Participants expressed a strong interest in explanations and training on analysis methods and software developed during the project, with a desire for dedicated training sessions.

Please note that the implementation strategy is based on a current co-design process. Therefore, the presented schema may change in the future.

2.1.2 Implementation

The EU-funded project Equal-Life (<https://equal-life.eu>) is coordinated by the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). They are responsible for the use of the content related to the project. For this reason, the toolbox modules will be maintained by RIVM. The long terms support strategy is under discussion.

The details about technologies and resources needed by each module will be discussed with RIVM at design/implementation phase. This strategy will preserve the contents and objects created for a longer time than the project.

2.1.3 Governance

The development process has two parallel branches, Exploration/Co-design and Implementation. The contents and methodology involved in both activities should follow the internal standards and regulations of the project. To ensure that, the development team set up recurring meetings with project managers and the RIVM IT team responsible for implementation.

2.1.4 Dissemination

A dedicated toolbox webpage is now available on Equal-Life website (<https://www.equal-life.eu/en/node/631>). The webpage gives a general explanation of the toolbox and its developments. There are also links to the objects currently available. During the toolbox development and implementation, getting updates on the development phase directly from this section will be possible.

Equal-Life is part of the EHEN network, and the toolbox will be integrated with the other EHEN projects toolboxes. To date, the integration process in the network is at the initial stage. A description of the modules of the Equal-Life toolbox will appear on the dedicated page of the EHEN network website: <https://www.humanexposome.eu/toolbox/>. Once available, the description will be linked to the online resource.

As described in the previous section of this document, the dissemination process, via training and seminars, will start in 2024.

2.2 Tools web design

Figma (<https://www.figma.com/>) represents a useful tool for prototyping and mocking the toolbox (See Figure 2 for a graphical overview of the exposed concepts).

The first beta version is available at the following link:

https://www.figma.com/file/79AE4rT7PVbFckYApAeovE/Project_brief_EL_toolbox?node-id=80%3A0

Comment-level access can be granted to all project partners who want to comment on the prototype directly. The Figma project represents a single space that allows collecting project ideas and comments from all developers. Quantia Consulting is responsible for the harmonization of comments and content.

The development team used the Wix platform (<http://wix.com>), a cloud-based web development service, to make the content accessible to the public as web pages based on the internal revision of the first prototype in Figma.

This CMS (content management system) with an easy-to-use management visual interface represents the primary development platform for the stakeholders' module prototype (blue square in Figure 4). The main reason behind choosing a CMS with an easy-to-use graphical interface is to allow multiple subjects within the project to modify the content during the testing phase.

2.3 The case studies

The Equal-Life consortium acknowledges the importance of the stakeholders' involvement in designing an efficient and usable tool. Therefore, the discussions with the stakeholders will shape the project's toolbox's structure and features.

During the definition phase, closer collaboration with a few partners is preferable to achieve a faster definition of needs and solutions. Amsterdam's Municipal Health service city (contact person: Fred Woudenberg, chair of the Municipal Health Service Amsterdam) and Utrecht (contact person: Miriam Weber, PI) were actively involved in the definition of toolbox design. Thanks to their roles as stakeholders, members of the External Advisory board, and PIs, they can offer a privileged view of the needs from a different perspective.

During this first design phase, the discussions focused on generic issues, including:

- Their vision of the relationship between exposure and impacts.
- Examples of problems that need to be solved at the city level and situations that need to be improved.
- Examples of good practices/good interventions.
- Recommendations for policy use, guidelines, and standards.
- Options for questions/discussions/consultations (Feedback information).

This collaboration aims to involve the selected stakeholders in the co-design phase, let them follow the implementation phase, provide feedback on the advanced proposals and test the advanced features in structured realities. More case studies will be considered in the future. The active participation of the stakeholders is scheduled for the first months of 2023.

2.3 The Stakeholder Module

The stakeholder module is designed as a website with interactive functions (an example is provided in Figure 3).

The main goals of this module are:

- Inform the stakeholder about the content of the Equal-Life project
- Collect information from the stakeholders

- Allow an interactive visualisation of the Equal-Life project results.
- Connect the stakeholder with the other modules of the toolkit

Figure 3: Web-page example of the Stakeholder module. The webpages are designed for a bi-directional interaction: give information and receive user feedback. In this specific example, the user is asked to enter their belonging organisation in a pop-up window.

The module will be integrated into the official Equal-Life website (<https://www.equal-life.eu/en>) as described in the general strategy section. However, a beta version, developed according to the scheme in Figure 4, is currently available for testing purposes. The hosting address of the prototype webpage is <https://www.stakeholder-equal-life.eu/>.

The contents present in the webpage pass an internal revision, both on texts and data sharing, by provisions adopted by RIVM (see the statement at the end of the session in this document)

A data store (Green square in Figure 4) will be connected to the web interface for persisting data collected by stakeholders. Information from the site (input elements) is collected via custom pop-ups in the web application. The web application exploits different graphic elements for interacting with users: text, checkboxes, calendars for collecting information, drop-down menus, and radio buttons for filtering the content.

The visitor can navigate content and view the aggregate statistics of all the data collected in the data store. The data store will be temporarily hosted within the storage space provided by the web development service. The service guarantees a Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate. The SSL certificate is a digital certificate that authenticates a website's identity and enables an encrypted connection.

The initial idea is to use the collected data to create descriptive statistics and visualizations in dashboards to be offered to stakeholders who use the form. A Python notebook, hosted in the Quantia GitHub account (Yellow square in Figure 4), currently contains the code to compute the statistics and generate the dashboard. The tables and views will be embedded in the web page to improve the accessibility and readability of the collected information.

The data collection operation and storage will comply with Dutch government guidelines following EU GDPR outlines for collecting, processing, and storing data. The collected data will not contain any sensitive information, will be collected and stored anonymously and will not include any identifier to link the collected data to the user who visited the website.

Figure 4: The general scheme of the beta version of the Stakeholder module.

2.4 The Visualization Module

The Visualization module will consist of a set of functions, tightly integrated but open to extension, supporting visualization and exploration of results obtained in the exposomes' experiments and implementations (regional or global). In addition, it will exploit advanced data dashboarding techniques to explore statistics related to essential aspects (e.g., schooling, social relationships, environment, etc.) publicly available at the European level.

This module will provide an interactive platform for exploring and presenting project results, making identifying key findings and insights easier. The dashboard can display a range of visualizations, such as charts, graphs, maps, and timelines, to represent the project's internal results. These visualizations can

provide an overview of the project's progress and highlight key metrics, such as the number of documents produced, the number of stakeholders involved, and the focus areas. In addition to displaying project data, the visualization module can allow for the exploration of metadata from stakeholders. This metadata can include information such as stakeholder demographics, their roles in the project, and their feedback on project outcomes. By providing access to this metadata, the module can enable stakeholders to better understand the project's findings and identify areas where further research or intervention may be needed.

Overall, a visualization module with a dashboard effectively makes sense of large data volumes and communicates project results to a wide range of stakeholders. By presenting information interactively and engagingly, the module can help to facilitate collaboration and drive meaningful change in the mental health domain.

The prototype is currently under development. A preview will be accessible from the stakeholder module website and available in June 2023.

2.5 The Semantic knowledge exploration module

A Semantic knowledge exploration module can help mental health researchers to efficiently and effectively analyse and understand large volumes of data, improve collaboration, and facilitate data-driven decision-making. In the Equal-Life toolbox, this module collects tools that can:

- **Efficiently analyse and understand large volumes of data:** A Semantic knowledge exploration module can help to automatically extract and analyse the meaning and context of large volumes of text data. This can help researchers to identify patterns, trends, and connections that may be difficult to detect through manual analysis.
- **Improve search accuracy:** The module can also help to improve search accuracy by identifying related concepts and synonyms. This can help to ensure that researchers can quickly find the information they need, even if the specific terminology used in the document may vary.
- **Enhance collaboration:** A Semantic knowledge exploration module can help enhance collaboration between researchers by facilitating the sharing and exploration of data more efficiently and meaningfully. This can help to ensure that all team members have access to the same information and can work together more effectively.
- **Facilitate data-driven decision-making:** By providing a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of the data, a Semantic knowledge exploration module can help researchers to make data-driven decisions. This can be particularly valuable in the field of mental health, where decisions can have a significant impact on the well-being of individuals and communities.

The module will include a range of features, such as natural language processing and machine learning algorithms, to help users navigate and visualize the data intuitively. The prototype, in stages of development will help users uncover previously unknown relationships between data points, allowing for new insights and discoveries. It can also will help users make more informed decisions based on the data, by providing a more complete and accurate understanding of the information at hand.

The Semantic knowledge exploration module will exploit NLP (Natural language processing) approaches that can ease the feature search and exploration capabilities for accessing the broader knowledge base of the project.

Furthermore, given the need to develop new data analysis techniques, the involved partners produced (and will produce) a substantial number of scientific publications and artifacts, both from a theoretical and practical point of view (with case studies). This production will be partly available, as well as in the scientific publication format, also as libraries and pipelines. These objects are generally hosted by third-party services with public access, such as GitLab, Bitbucket, etc...

These contents will be indexed within the module's tools to facilitate the use of these contents for users who wish to use them.

The prototype is currently under development. A preview will be accessible from the stakeholder module website and available in June 2023.

3. Conclusions and Future Actions

The research on mental health and cognitive development, where the source of the considered factors is more comprehensive than in formal studies, highlighted the need for tools that support the exploration of information and data to guide less experienced users in accessing such content. Indeed, the lack of tools that accomplish this goal is mainly due to the complexity of the subject matter. The tool's design to display heterogeneous information with an easy interface represents a very complex task and is one of the primary purposes of Equal-Life.

At the project's current status, we defined:

- The number and type of modules (Figure 2) that will be developed during the project's duration
- The categories of final users
- The possible data sources

The first step of the prototyping phase was the definition of the data access methodologies (e.g., dashboard, semantic search, etc.). The toolbox's overall functionalities were defined as different modules that can be independently developed based on the data availability. Co-design actions are still open until the end of 2023. The implementation status of the modules will be reported in future deliverables (D9.3 - Prototype for Data e knowledge exploration tool and D9.7 - Tool for Data and Knowledge Exploration Assessment).

The meeting and surveys related to the exploration and co-design step in WP8/WP9 highlighted some critical issues currently under resolution. In particular, the need for a shared glossary to ease the participation of different actors in the design of the various modules is under internal discussion. The problem will be addressed by defining the ontology for semantic search tools.

The definition of some specific terms, such as those used to define development objects (toolbox, toolkit, tool), is now successfully delivered. The different internal working groups are still addressing open issues, such as the validity context of the provided definitions of toolbox-related terms.

The development strategy based on co-design increases usability (if the product is seen to the user's needs, it is more likely to be used). But it does show downsides in scheduling the work required for effective product development.

As shown in Annex 1 (Gantt chart), the working prototypes of all modules are due by the end of 2023. To achieve this goal, the Exploration / Co-Design cycle should end during the summer of 2023. After the prototyping phase, the implementation phase will follow. This step will define the toolbox's long-term maintenance strategies in detail. We will also proceed to the testing phase with selected case studies that will emerge during the scheduled workshops. The training meetings represent the best setting for testing the toolbox's functionalities.

3.1 Deviations from the work plan

Deliverable 9.3 "Prototype for Data e knowledge exploration tool" was postponed from M36 to M43

Deliverable 9.6 "Training Protocol and Deployments", has been postponed from M46 to M52.

Deliverable 9.7 "Tool for Data and Knowledge Exploration Assessment", has been postponed to M56 from M46.

4. Glossary

Toolbox:

The set of IT tools that will be developed within the Equal-life project. The term "toolbox" refers to the object that includes all the tools as a whole.

Toolkit:

A synonym for toolbox

Tool: In the context of Equal-Life project, a tool refers to any software, hardware, or documentation designed to support the needs and requirements of stakeholders interested in the project or internal partners. For example, documentation such as project plans, status reports, and requirements documents can also serve as tools to help stakeholders understand project goals, progress, and requirements. Training programs and user guides can also help stakeholders learn how to use tools and participate effectively in the project. Also, software, library, or pipeline that will be developed is considered a tool.

Stakeholders may have different needs depending on their roles in the project, such as project managers, team members, customers, or external partners. Tools can be used to address these needs

and provide stakeholders with the necessary information, resources, and support to participate in the project effectively.

Web application:

A computer program that utilizes web browsers and web technology to perform tasks over the Internet.

(Source: <https://www.stackpath.com/edge-academy/what-is-a-web-application/>)

Module:

An extension to the main program dedicated to a specific function.

Library:

A collection of non-volatile resources used by computer programs, often for software development. These may include configuration data, documentation, help data, message templates, pre-written code and subroutines, classes, values or type specifications. (Source:

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Library_\(computing\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Library_(computing)))

Repository:

A central place in which an aggregation of data or software packages is kept and maintained in an organised way, usually in computer storage. They can be public or private.

Annex 1 Gantt chart Development Plan

Annex 1: Gantt chart of the toolbox development stages described in the main text.

